

Guidance for Students on Using Legal Texts in Solving Case Studies in Civic Education

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ABSTRACT: To help students understand, remember, and expand their knowledge; while enhancing their ability to apply knowledge in practice; promote the initiative and enthusiasm of learners; and, in particular, develop students' skills in using legal documents in performing general academic tasks and solving specific case studies, teachers must explore and create new teaching methods and techniques. The use of legal documents in teaching in general, and in solving situational exercises in particular, will be a new direction in the innovation of teaching and learning the subject of Civic Education in grade 12. *"Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject to improve the effectiveness of teaching the subject"* is one of the new teaching methods I have used in the past school year. After a year of experimenting with this teaching method at Thang Long Specialized High School in Da Lat, it has helped students better understand the lesson content, retain knowledge longer, expand their legal knowledge beyond the textbook, and especially encouraged students to apply their knowledge in real-life situations. Additionally, this teaching method has effectively enhanced students' self-learning abilities and their proactive approach to learning; particularly, it has begun to develop students' skills in using legal documents to solve subject-specific scenario-based exercises. This, in turn, has improved the quality of teaching in the subject. The study was conducted in two classes (the experimental group was 12SD and 12 Biology, and the control group was 12 IT and 12 French – these two classes were of equivalent levels) at Thang Long Specialized High School in Da Lat. The 12SD and 12 Sinh classes were selected as the experimental group, and the 12 IT and 12 French classes were selected as the control group. The experimental class was taught using the method of *"Guiding students to use legal texts in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject."* The control class was taught using traditional teaching methods. call data used for analysis and evaluation were collected from tests developed according to the Ministry of Education and Training's common standards and from sociological survey forms. Data collection was conducted in both the experimental and control classes. Specifically: For data collected from tests: Tests were administered to both the experimental and control classes. The tests were conducted before (one test) and after the experiment (using the results of three different tests). The sociological survey was conducted once before the experiment and once after the experiment for the experimental class group (the first survey was conducted concurrently with the pre-experiment test, and the second survey was conducted concurrently with the third test after the experiment).

The test results of the experimental group between the pre-experiment test and the third post-experiment test were 0.71 points (7.84 before the experiment and 8.55 in the third post-experiment test). The probability of the post-impact test was $p = 0.00017$ (***the results could not have occurred randomly but were due to the impact***).

The learning outcomes through student tests were improved with specific values: The average post-intervention test score for the experimental class was 8.55, while the average test score for the control class was 8.0. Here, the intervention group had a higher average score than the control group, with a score difference of 0.55 points between the two groups (*indicating a significant difference*).

The probability of the post-intervention test $p = 0.0007554$ ($p < 0.05$) proves that the difference in the average values of the two classes in the third test after the intervention is significant (***the result is not likely to occur randomly but is due to the result of the intervention***).

The difference in the mean values of the two groups after the intervention in the third test after the intervention, $SMD = 1.0$, indicates that the impact of the intervention is large, meaning that the intervention measures in the study had a significant effect on the learning outcomes of the experimental group.

The correlation coefficient between the pre-intervention test results and the post-intervention test results for the experimental group (12 SD and 12 Biology) is at an average level (0.32).

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The results of the sociological survey conducted in the experimental class show that *"Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in Grade 12 GDCD"* helps students better understand the content of the knowledge they have learned, improves their memory, expands their knowledge, and, in particular, improves their ability to apply the knowledge they have learned in practice. Along with that, the use of this teaching method has more effectively promoted students' learning abilities, making them more active and proactive in the process of performing their learning tasks. Students' skills in using legal documents have begun to take shape and develop further. Although not yet as expected, this is a noteworthy result. These positive changes have contributed significantly to improving students' learning outcomes.

Based on the above results, we can conclude that *"Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject"* has improved the effectiveness of teaching the subject.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Current Situation

Most 12th graders today do not really focus on studying Civic Education. In the minds of many students, this is a minor subject (*69.5% of students surveyed consider it a minor subject, 9% consider it a major subject, and 21.5% are unsure*), and they set overly high goals for their grades in this subject (*47% of students say their goal is to achieve average to above-average grades*). Although in recent years, Civic Education has been included as one of the subjects in the high school graduation exam, most students only use their Civic Education scores for graduation purposes, so they have the mindset that they only need to achieve a passing score on the exam (*53% of respondents chose a score range of 5.0 to below 7.5, 33% chose a target score range of 7.5 to below 8.0, and 14% set a target score of 8.0 or above*). This is precisely why they do not spend much time studying the subject.

Many students do not fully understand the content of the lessons, and they face difficulties in memorizing, expanding, and applying knowledge to practical situations; their proactivity and enthusiasm in learning is not high; in particular, many students lack the skills to use legal documents in performing general learning tasks and solving situational exercises in particular; this leads to difficulties in solving situational exercises.

The high-level application scenarios in Grade 12 Civic Education used by teachers in the learning process, as well as the scenarios in current exam questions, tend to be lengthy, with many characters appearing and many details that confuse students. These types of scenarios truly spark students' curiosity and interest in performing tasks, but they do not promote creativity in students' learning.

The 12th grade Civic Education subject has a relatively large amount of knowledge, while the time allocated for classroom learning is only one period per week. With this amount of time, teachers only have enough time to teach theory, and the application of knowledge in practice through the handling of hypothetical and real-life exercises is very limited, so most teachers will choose teaching methods that allow them to actively ensure time, such as presentations, reading and copying, projecting and copying, one-way monologues, etc. They pay little attention to active teaching methods or methods that develop students' skills.

To improve the effectiveness of teaching the subject, over the past years, teachers teaching Civic Education 12 in schools have sought to innovate teaching methods in various ways, but the results have not been as expected. The innovations have not fully harnessed the positive and proactive nature of students in the learning process, particularly in helping students form and develop the skills to use legal documents in performing learning tasks, including solving situational exercises. These limitations prevent the learning process from fully exploiting students' learning abilities, leading to Civic Education 12 learning outcomes that are not commensurate with their learning abilities.

Based on the above reality, I have chosen the topic *"Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject to improve the effectiveness of teaching the subject"* as my research direction.

1.2 Alternative solutions

"Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in Grade 12 Civic Education" will improve the effectiveness of teaching the subject through the results of tests between the experimental class and the control class.

Many authors have previously researched and proposed various solutions for innovating the teaching methods of Civic Education in secondary schools, including the use of teaching scenarios and the integration of legal knowledge in the teaching process of specific subjects, such as:

Nguyen Thi Thanh Mai (2011), *Building and Using Situations in Teaching Law in High Schools*, Doctoral Dissertation, Vietnam Institute of Educational Sciences.

Dao Thi Huong (2011), *Using the Scenario Method Combined with Role-Playing in Teaching Civic Education in Grade 12*, Master's Thesis, Vinh University.

Hoang Thi Hong Hanh (2014), *Combining group discussion and case studies in teaching Civic Education to 12th graders*, Van Ban High School No. 1, Lao Cai.

Phan Thi Van Thuy (2017), *Some measures to effectively integrate legal texts into some 12th grade GDCD lessons at high schools*, Gia Hoi High School, Thua Thien Hue.

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Ha Thi Hanh (2015), *Applying practical situations to teaching certain Grade 12 Civic Education lessons to enhance student interest and learning outcomes*, Van Ban High School No. 3, Lao Cai.

Duong Thi Hoai Dung, *Using situational exercises in teaching 12th grade Civic Education lessons*, Dao Duy Tu High School, Quang Binh.

Pham Thi Khuyen (2019), *Using problem-based scenarios in teaching certain GDCD lessons for Grade 12*, Quan Hoa High School, Thanh Hoa.

Mai Thi Giang (2019), *Integrating Legal Education into Teaching the Lesson: Implementing the Law – Civic Education 12*, Hau Loc 3 High School, Thanh Hoa.

Bui Huu Vinh (2021), *Integrating New Legal Content into Teaching Civic Education 12*, Yen Thanh 3 High School, Nghe An.

Previous articles and studies have proposed measures for effectively using case studies in teaching the 12th grade Civic Education subject; some topics have addressed the use of legal documents to teach the subject – solving case studies. However, no topic has guided students on how to effectively use legal documents to solve the case studies presented.

Therefore, the topic "*Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject to improve teaching effectiveness*" is a new and necessary direction.

2.3 Research Issues

2.3.1. Formulating research questions

Does "*Guiding students to use legal texts in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject*" help students understand the knowledge they have learned? How does the ability to remember, expand, and apply learned knowledge in practice differ from the old teaching method? How has the proactivity and positivity of learners changed? In particular, have students developed skills in using legal texts? Finally, have the above changes led to improved learning outcomes for students?

2.3.2. Research Hypothesis

Guiding students to use legal documents in solving situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education subject will improve students' learning outcomes.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research Subjects.

The subjects selected for this study are four 12th-grade classes in the 2022-2023 academic year at Thang Long Specialized High School - Da Lat. These are: 12 SD, 12 Biology, 12 IT and 12 French.

The selected classes share similarities in academic quality and training.

3.2. Research design

*) Selection of research subjects:

Select 4 classes: 12 SD, 12 Biology, 12 IT, 12 French and divide these 4 classes into 2 groups, namely:

+ Experimental group: Class 12 SD, 12 Biology

+ Control group: Class 12 IT, 12 LA

*) Selecting the appropriate statistical test:

- Design a pre- and post-test for equivalent groups (design 2). The equivalent groups in the test are the two classes: Class 12 SD, 12 Biology (experimental class); Class 12 IT, 12 French (control class).

Table 1. Research design and statistics

Class group	Effect	Test
Experimental (12 SD, 12 Biology)	Teaching approach: " <i>Guiding students to use legal texts in solving case studies in Civic Education</i> "	Verification method Paired t-test Correlation coefficient
Control	Normal teaching (Solving situational	Hypothesis testing

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(12 IT, 12 French)	exercises without using legal documents).	Paired t-test Correlation coefficient
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Pre-impact verification using an independent t-test to determine whether the two classes are equivalent in terms of pre-impact test results. Use the regular test in the first semester as the pre-impact test to determine whether the two groups are equivalent, and use the results of the three post-impact tests to compare with the pre-impact results - impact to confirm the effectiveness of the solution.

Intervention: Experimental class group (Grade 12 SD, 12 Biology): Apply the method "Using legal texts in solving situational exercises" to the following topics:

- + **Lesson 2:** Implementation of the law.
- + **Topic:** Equal treatment of citizens before the law.
- + **Lesson 5:** Equal Rights Among Ethnic Groups and Religions.
- + **Lesson 6:** Citizens and their fundamental freedoms.
- + **Lesson 7:** Citizens and democratic rights.
- + **Lesson 8:** Law and the development of citizens.

Control group: Lessons taught using traditional methods.

Use midterm I, final I, and midterm II exams (45-minute tests) to assess post-intervention effects (questions developed according to the Ministry of Education and Training's guidelines). Post-intervention verification using the independent t-test and SMD index to determine whether the post-experimental test results could have occurred randomly. Simultaneously, determine the extent to which the solution affects students' learning outcomes.

* Designing the pre-survey questionnaire:

- Conduct surveys with the experimental group before and after the experimental teaching.
- Data is processed in percentage terms to draw conclusions about the issue
- The survey form was designed as a sociological survey form with continuous responses.

3.3. Research process and timeline

3.3.1 Teacher preparation:

- + Prepare a teaching plan focused on "Guiding students to use legal documents in solving case studies." The content of the report only illustrates a teaching plan focused on "Using legal documents in solving case studies." Specifically, this is the Lesson Plan for **Lesson 2: Implementing the Law**.
- + Design an electronic lesson plan to illustrate the designed teaching plan. The report content only illustrates one electronic lesson plan.
 - + Prepare the survey questionnaire content.
 - + Develop a test.
 - + Research Excel algorithms for processing collected data.
 - + Ask teachers from the same subject to supervise and grade the test to ensure reliability.

3.3.2 Conducting the experimental teaching:

The timing of the experimental teaching follows the school's teaching plan and schedule to ensure objectivity. Specifically as follows:

Table 2. Experimental Timeline (Grade 12 SD)

Experimen tal Period	Period PPCT	Implementation Content	Notes
Week 1 and 2	1+2	- Lesson 1. Law and Life - Teach using traditional methods. - Conduct a pre-experimental	- The test is structured like a regular exam.

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		assessment.	
Weeks 3, 4, 5	3+4+5	<p>Lesson 2. Implementing the law</p> <p>- Teach using the approach:</p> <p><i>"Using legal documents in solving case studies"</i></p>	
Week 6	6	<p>Special Topic: Equal Treatment of Citizens Under the Law.</p> <p>- Teaching approach: <i>Using legal documents to solve case studies</i></p>	
Weeks 7+8	7 + 8	<p>Review and mid-term exam</p>	<p>The exam is structured according to the specifications issued by the Ministry of Education and</p>

			Training.
Weeks 9, 10, 11	9+10+11	<p>- Topic: Equal Rights Before the Law.</p> <p>- Teaching Approach: <i>Using legal documents to solve case studies.</i></p>	
Weeks 12, 13	12+13	<p>- Lesson 5. Equality among ethnic groups and religions.</p> <p>- Teaching approach: <i>Using legal texts in solving case studies</i></p>	
Weeks 14, 15	14+15	<p>- Lesson 6: Citizens and their fundamental freedoms.</p> <p>- Teaching approach: <i>Using legal documents to solve case studies.</i></p>	

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Week 16	16	Extracurricular activity on drug prevention and HIV/AIDS	
Week 17	17	Review of Semester I	
Week 18	18	Regular Exam	The exam is structured according to the specifications issued by the Ministry of Education and Training.
Weeks 19 +20+21	19, 20, 21	- Lesson 6: Citizens and their fundamental freedoms. - Teaching approach: <i>Using legal documents to solve case studies.</i>	
Week 22+23	22+23	Lesson 7. Citizens and their democratic rights.	

		- Teaching approach: <i>Using legal documents to solve case studies</i>	
Week 24+25	24+25	- Lesson 8. Law and the Development of Citizens. - Teaching approach: <i>Using legal documents to solve case studies</i>	

3.4. Measurement and data collection

- **Data collection:** Based on pre- and post-impact results. Method of implementation: Knowledge assessment test.
- **Measurement tools used:**
- + The pre-intervention assessment is the regular exam for the first semester of the 2022– 2023 academic year.
- + Post-intervention test:
- > Test 1: Midterm test for the first semester of the 2022–2023 academic year.

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- > Test 2: The final exam of the first semester of the 2022–2023 academic year.
- > Test 3: Midterm exam for the second semester of the 2022–2023 academic year.
- + The survey was conducted beforehand (concurrently with the regular midterm exam for the first semester of the 2022–2023 academic year) and after the experiment for the experimental class (concurrently with the midterm exam for the second semester of the 2022–2023 academic year).

- **Verification of validity:**

- + The test questions and answers are developed based on the knowledge, skills, and attitudes standards set by the Ministry of Education and Training.
- + The survey form is developed based on the Likert scale.

- **Reliability verification:**

- + Have other teachers re-grade the tests.
- + Use Excel to process survey forms.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. For management levels

- For the Department of Education and Training:

- + Strengthen training on innovative teaching methods that promote students' self-learning abilities; develop skills, including the ability to search for and use legal documents in solving learning tasks and situations that arise in students' future lives.
- + Strengthen training to improve the legal knowledge of the teaching staff. Currently, due to the nature of the 12th grade civic education subject, which is legal knowledge, if teachers do not have legal knowledge, they will not be able to effectively guide students in using legal documents in performing general learning tasks and solving specific situational exercises.

- For schools:

- + Develop plans and strengthen the inspection and evaluation of teaching method innovations oriented towards developing students' abilities and qualities. Inspections can be carried out through lesson observations, teacher competitions, teaching plans, etc. There should be a mechanism to encourage teachers to research applied pedagogical sciences, which is currently lacking in secondary schools.
- + Invest in equipping facilities for teaching and learning activities: Establish legal libraries, regularly update new legal documents, equip projectors, computers with internet access, speakers, etc.
- + Supervise and inspect teachers' participation in professional training, especially training on innovative teaching methods.

4.2. For teachers

4.2.1. In terms of awareness

- Correctly understand the role of teaching method innovation as the key to educational reform. Innovation must be carried out in a student-centered manner; it must ensure the development of students' qualities and abilities.
- Correctly understand the importance of using legal documents in teaching legal knowledge in the 12th grade Civic Education subject, especially in teaching legal case studies.

4.2.2. In terms of practice:

- Improve professional competence and legal knowledge: In order to guide students in the effective use of legal documents in teaching, especially in solving legal situations, each teacher must have broad legal knowledge and the skills to read, exploit, and use legal documents effectively. To achieve this goal, teachers can participate in professional training sessions, self-study, etc.
- Improve pedagogical skills: Guiding students to effectively use legal documents in teaching, especially in resolving legal situations, will only be effective when teachers combine it with other teaching methods. For teachers to effectively combine with other teaching methods without forcing them, teachers must master teaching methods and understand the advantages and disadvantages of each method.

To guide students in effectively using legal documents to solve situational exercises in the 12th grade Civic Education course during the teaching process, I have drawn the following conclusions:

a) *Teachers guide students to correctly identify the relevant to resolve the given situation:*

As we know, in the learning process, as well as in real life, some legal situations require students to use legal documents in order to come up with answers. Therefore, the first thing to do when approaching such a situation is to correctly identify the legal documents that govern the relationships in that situation. If the correct legal document cannot be identified or is identified

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incorrectly, it will be impossible to provide an answer in such situations. Identifying the correct legal documents to handle situational exercises is not an easy task for students; therefore, it requires teachers to guide students so that they can access the correct legal documents, or in other words, teachers must show students which legal documents to use to handle a given legal situation.

To guide students in correctly identifying and finding the right legal documents, teachers must have a solid knowledge of the law, regularly access and search for legal documents, and be very well prepared. To ensure sufficient class time, teachers must determine the necessary legal documents before class.

Example 1: Lesson 2: Law enforcement. Section 2. Violations of the law and legal responsibility.

Situation: *A, aged 16, was riding an Ablack motorcycle with a cylinder capacity of 150cm³ with his father to the bus station to pick up a relative. Due to unfamiliarity with the road and failure to see the sign, A and his father drove the motorcycle against the direction of a one-way street. Immediately, the father and son were stopped by law enforcement officers for inspection and a report was filed. However, A's father refused to pay the fine on the grounds that he did not recognize the one-way road sign and that A was only 16 years old, still a minor, and was only following his father, so he should not be fined.*

4.3 For parents of students

- The mindset of viewing Civic Education as a minor subject should be eliminated.
- Encourage and provide the best possible conditions in terms of time and equipment for their children's learning process.
- Change the mindset regarding the academic performance of Civic Education for their children. The academic performance in Civic Education is not just about grades; what is most important is the attitude and actions of the students.

4.4 For students

- Be proactive and active in completing academic tasks. Seek out, read, and research the legal documents provided by teachers; analyze, evaluate, and draw conclusions about learning situations.
- Foster a spirit of teamwork.
- Focus on developing the general competencies of students: self-learning, problem-solving, self-management, creativity, language use, communication, cooperation, information filtering, and use of information technology.

CONCLUSION

Guiding students in using legal texts to solve case studies in Civic Education not only contributes to improving learning effectiveness but also helps them develop the legal skills necessary for modern life. Through the process of familiarizing themselves with, researching, and applying legal provisions to specific situations, students gradually learn to think logically, analyze issues based on legal grounds, and ensure objectivity in their assessments. This makes lessons more lively and relevant to real life, while also fostering a sense of respect for and compliance with the law—an important quality for citizens in society. In addition, practicing the skill of interpreting legal texts also contributes to innovating teaching methods, shifting the role of students from passive recipients to active explorers of knowledge, enabling them to independently seek information and defend their opinions based on clear legal grounds. Therefore, guiding students in using legal texts to solve situational exercises needs to be organized regularly, scientifically, and in accordance with the cognitive characteristics of each grade level, thereby contributing to improving the quality of teaching Civic Education and legal awareness education for the younger generation.

REFERENCES

- 1) Nguyen Thi Thanh Mai (2011), Building and Using Situations in Teaching Law in High Schools, Doctoral Dissertation, Vietnam Institute of Educational Sciences.
- 2) Dao Thi Huong (2011), Using the Scenario Method Combined with Role-Playing in Teaching Civic Education in Grade 12, Master's Thesis, Vinh University.
- 3) Hoang Thi Hong Hanh (2014), Combining Group Discussion Methods and Using Scenarios in Teaching Civic Education for Grade 12, Van Ban High School No. 1, Lao Cai.
- 4) Phan Thi Van Thuy (2017), Some measures to effectively integrate legal texts into some 12th grade GDCD lessons at high schools, Gia Hoi High School, Thua Thien Hue.
- 5) Ha Thi Hanh (2015), Applying practical situations to teaching some Grade 12 Civic Education lessons to enhance students' interest and learning outcomes, Van Ban High School No. 3, Lao Cai.
- 6) Duong Thi Hoai Dung, Using situational exercises in teaching 12th grade Civic Education lessons, Dao Duy Tu High School, Quang Binh.
- 7) Pham Thi Khuyen (2019), Using problem-based scenarios in teaching certain GDCD lessons for Grade 12, Quan Hoa High School, Thanh Hoa.
- 8) Mai Thi Giang (2019), Integrating Legal Education into Teaching the Lesson: Implementing the Law – Civic Education 12, Hau Loc 3 High School, Thanh Hoa.
- 9) Bui Huu Vinh (2021), Integrating New Legal Content into Teaching Civic Education 12, Yen Thanh 3 High School, Nghe An.